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eContentplus

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¹ OJ L 79, 24.3.2005, p. 1.

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PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The JEM thematic network aims to contribute to the quality of eContent for mathematics and to advance the adoption of computer technology in the teaching and learning of mathematics.

Due to its nature, large parts of mathematics instruction, from homework and practice to actual assessment, can be automated. Mathematics is also universal: high quality content and services do not need, in many cases, other localization than translation. Content developed in Finland, can be used almost as such in South Africa.

It has been widely recognized that the level of mathematical competence of its citizens is a strategic asset for any country. Despite of the high potential of eContent and services, mathematics remains a subject in which the instruction still happens mostly in the traditional way. The offered instructional content and services need to improve, and the teachers need to be trained to use these services. This is what the JEM Network does. High-quality eContent and related services for mathematics can make a difference by being reusable, interactive and easily delivered to students' computers worldwide.

The goal of the JEM thematic network is to create a community blending the expertise of technology developers, the authors and users in order to contribute to the coordination of content enrichment activities in the area of mathematics, and to promote the established standards and best practices.

The community portal aims, e.g., to deliver synoptic user information and support pages to advance the uptake of technologies in eLearning for mathematics.

The JEM network organizes events to raise the awareness among educational content stakeholders in mathematics on the benefits of enriching digital content with semantic markup. Additionally, technology developers are placed in touch with authors of digital content. JEM enlists the leading developers of the technologies as instructors and tutors for author of eContent and, as a result, distributes best practice sample material via established servers of major universities, commercial publishers and professional societies, like the European Mathematical Society.

The JEM portal offers a social networking platform that identifies the community of experts in eContent for mathematics. By including authors, developers and distributors, and end-users, the JEM portal collects and records reusable documentation on the workflows of mathematical eContent.

JEM events are attended by participants of other community-funded projects, that are close to the area of eContent for mathematics, thus establishing the network as a dissemination channel for the community.

CONSORTIUM

The JEM network currently enlists 20 nodes, which are eContent stakeholders for the area of mathematics, physics or statistics education.

The technology developer partners include the leading European groups producing advanced learning software solutions. They offer a wide range of ICT tools to

enhance the teaching of mathematics. They include University of Helsinki, TU/e, Technical University of Eindhoven, Jacobs University and NAG Ltd, with a long tradition in research on the representation and software for the electronic communication of mathematics. The commercial partner Maths for More has released several tools and plugins that can be used in the Moodle learning environment, including a math-enabled chat application. University of Birmingham offers and continues to develop STACK, an advanced software system for mathematics assessment, which generates random exercises and automatically grades the students' answers. Recently it has also produced a mathematics editor applet that can be used in Moodle or standalone to enter easily a mathematical expression.

RWTH Aachen University, and ISN Oldenburg offer full online learning environments for teaching applications of mathematics in Statistics and Physics. Advanced multilingual software is the expertise of Chalmers University of Technology.

Several partners are experienced authors of online educational material for mathematics and their institutions offer online courses and distance education. Universiteit van Amsterdam has a wide experience in using ICT-supported courseware. Three JEM partners represent purely virtual universities: the German FernUniversität Hagen, the Spanish UNED National Distance University of Education, and the Catalanian Universitat Oberta de Catalunya. All of them deliver instruction purely online. Universidade de Lisboa, Buskerud University College, and Aristotle University of Thessaloniki are traditional higher education institutions where the introduction of ICT support is taking place gradually. Trondheim NTNU, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, joins JEM as an institution for training mathematics teachers.

Whilst all partners have specific dissemination channels, consisting of a network of students, or organizations or professional societies, the JEM network also includes the commercial publisher Liguori Editori and the major international academic society of professional mathematicians, the European Mathematical Society.

The consortium is currently not accepting any new members.

PROJECT RESULTS/ACHIEVEMENTS

The JEM network has pursued its goal of bridging the gaps between communities involved in mathematics education by organizing events bringing the major stakeholders together. The 3rd JEM workshop in Barcelona at the end of January 2008, was attended by a number of participants outside the network. Most notably, the coordinator of the @Science Thematic Network, and several members of the InterGeo project have presented their work during our meetings. This led to further contacts and exchanges, especially with the mathematics accessibility community.

The 3rd JEM workshop was also hosting a special session on the OpenMath3 effort of alignment with the most recent MathML3 specification. This work on standards for electronic communication of mathematics is actively pursued by several members of the JEM network and led by M. Kohlhase on the OpenMath3 side, and by D. Carlisle on the MathML3 side. A major rewrite of the chapter on content-mathml is underway and affects the collection of OpenMath Content Dictionaries since it plans to adopt OpenMath symbols in its representation. To be successful, this work has to be carried out in cooperation with the OpenMath Society and with the relevant user groups

(including the Science and InterGeo project).

The online proceedings of the 3rd JEM workshop are available from the portal. The 4th JEM meeting has been postponed to take place in September alongside with the 4th European Workshop on Mathematical & Scientific e-Contents and is organized as a day of tutorials and hands-on sessions. The JEM network has also sponsored smaller seminars, including the second SCOOP workshop on Scientific Communities of Practice, hosted in Bremen at the end of June 2008. This topic is gaining increasing attention and a similar meeting be organized also the next year. Online proceedings are available from the JEM portal.

A new repository for learning resources, based on LOM metadata, has been added to the JEM portal. The repository accepts descriptions of learning resources in several languages, these can be tagged by keyword chosen by the user and searched or browsed conveniently via a variety of facets, including topic, author, and language. Community comments and reviews are enabled for the entries in the repository so that end-users of the eContent may give public feedback to authors. This option is not yet being used by the JEM community, probably because not accustomed to open reviewing. JEM resources are made available to everyone without requiring prior registration to the JEM portal whereas it is required for entering a learning resource in the JEM repository.

The software running the repository has been created as a Drupal module and is also available for downloading, together with the vocabulary for classifying the resources. It has been adopted by INITE, Universidad Tecnológica de México, who also contributed the Spanish translation of the repository guide.

The JEM portal is supporting multilinguality, namely pages can be translated to several languages and will appear in the language of choice, if a translation exist. These translations are done on a volunteer basis, like any other contribution to the portal.

TARGET USERS & THEIR NEEDS

The JEM user community consists of developers of supporting technologies for mathematics, authors of eContents and users of eContent in the teaching of mathematics. All these groups benefit from exchanging views on how technology should be developed and how it is used in an educational context. JEM provides such a forum and organizes meetings where the presentations cover all the aspects involved in employing eContent in mathematical education.

The developers of technologies for enhancing eContent in mathematics are supported by JEM in their dissemination efforts by the availability of "Software and services" pages on the JEM portal. These are designed to give quick, informative descriptions, links and demonstrations to those who wish to further develop or use the software. After registration on the JEM site, it is possible to create such a description page and to maintain it regularly, using it as a way to direct JEM readers to one's own products. The member's blog can also serve this purpose and provide a ready to use way to publish news concerning releases, new features, patches, and so on.

For authors of eContent and, in particular, for authors wishing to share or recommend learning resources, the JEM portal offers a fully LOM-compliant repository which is integrated with the free-tagging mechanism and with the comment and open

reviews facility. JEM members may describe using standard metadata a resource and add a link for it. Since very recently, it is also possible to import LOM metadata from elsewhere thus facilitating the upload and registration of resources previously registered elsewhere. Each resource cataloged in the repository can be openly commented and/or reviewed formally by other members. Notice that it is possible to browse and comment the repository content without being a registered user of JEM, however this is not sufficient for adding a new resource.

The JEM repository is also acting as an OAI data provider that can be queried according to standard protocols of digital archives.

For users of eContent, the JEM portal offers a listing of case studies, which may be consulted freely online. To enter a new case study, members need to compile a basic form, which outlines briefly the structure of the description. This can be augmented by linking publications or URLs to it. The list of case studies is intended as a collection that can be best enlarged by the mathematics educators or by researchers in mathematics education since each case study can provide pedagogical guidelines on where and how to introduce technology in eLearning mathematics.

In general, the interests of the JEM community are easily seen from the JEM "tag cloud". Each tag on the JEM portal has an RSS feed associated with it, this means that tagging an item can be used both for dissemination purposes and for subscription purposes. Take for instance the tag "OpenMath", all news, blogs, events and pages which are tagged with it are listed on <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/taxonomy/term/8> and any user interested in OpenMath may subscribe to the RSS feed by pointing it to the corresponding feed <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/taxonomy/term/8/feed>. This mechanism can readily be employed, by all JEM community members, to promote their activities, and to keep up-to-date with their interest.

UNDERLYING CONTENT

The content produced by the members of the JEM network is contributed to the portal on a volunteer basis. Since the intent of the network is to disseminate best practice, the material distributed by the JEM portal aims to showcase what is now possible in eContent for mathematics by using a blend of technologies.

At the time of writing, the recorded publications available from the website amounted to 183 items including full online courses, papers, slide presentations and tutorials. In general, all presentations delivered during a JEM sponsored event are archived on the website. All network deliverables are archived and can be downloaded as pdf or consulted online, the full list is located at the portal address <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/publications/deliverables>. The portal contains sections for learning resources, at present about 70 sample resources are registered using LOM metadata, in addition to 8 case studies and 23 descriptions of software and services.

Resources and content published via the JEM portal is subject to community review and as such it is the community, which decides its quality. The number of downloads or of hits of a certain resource is recorded for each entry and yields a rough measure of usage.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

The JEM network activities have concentrated on ensuring a solid performance for the portal pages which serve the community. This included the development of a software package based on the Drupal CMS for the implementation of the JEM repository. The accompanying guide was released and has obtained considerable attention. By producing a LOM-compliant module for a repository running in one of the most adopted content management systems, JEM has contributed to advance the adoption of a standard metadata format for describing learning resources. In the specific case of mathematics, the same classification vocabulary, as is used on JEM, can be also adopted by other sites setting up learning repositories. The future work includes providing and enhancing the repository with the OAI-PMH interface, Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, which will turn the JEM repository to both a data and a service provider. This effort aims to make the JEM repository completely interoperable with the repositories run by members such as ISN Oldenburg, UvA and UOC.

All the partners have followed up in their activities as documented in their progress reports, online at <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/about/progress> for registered users. In particular, University of Birmingham has released a math editor called DragMath which can be used in Moodle. Also Maths for More has produced plugins for Moodle, including a chat application which allows to type mathematical expressions. UNED and UOC have started cooperation with Maths for More to integrate their products in their learning environments. GeoGebra has gained increasing attention within the JEM community after their attendance at the 3rd JEM workshop, with NTNU, Buskerud, Birmingham and UNED reporting work for adopting it in their courses.

Alternative learning environments are being studied at Jacobs University with a specific attention to supporting scientific communities of practice and semantic wikis. Enhancements of wiki-like platforms for education are also done in Chalmers with software for automated multilingual translation of wiki pages.

Considerable progress has been made to align OpenMath3 and MathML3 with respect to the representation of the meaning of mathematical expressions in terms of an agreed collection of symbols. The adoption of the mechanism of Content Dictionaries by both languages will have a positive impact for the implementation of software supporting semantic markup, since it will be enough to provide one encoding only. In addition to this, the release of the STIX fonts in the public domain will make it easier to widely distribute mathematical documents without relying on TeX fonts, for example, which are typically only available in non standard encodings and formats. JEM partners, Jacobs University and TU/e, have continued to develop software and tools handling the extension languages OMDoc and MathDox.

An integrated FormulaEditor is now available as part of MathDox and work is in progress to add an intelligent feedback component for linear algebra and the notion of adaptive context.

Several JEM members also author courses for distance education and elearning in mathematics. FernUniversität Hagen improved their flashcard-based content used in single variable calculus distance course. Likewise, University of Helsinki has reorganized its extensive collection of interactive exercises and produced a full online course on Calculus which won the Rector's prize for technology in education.

Interactive exercises for Basic Mathematics have been created, improved and tested further by UvA for diagnostic assessment of incoming students of Science. Several JEM partners have developed courses for the training of mathematics teachers.

Technology offers ways to industrialize instruction, especially in mathematics. Finding pedagogically sound solutions and ways to use technology is, right now, the most pressing issue. The last year of the Network will be devoted to these matters. Technology can be used to automate parts of the mathematics instruction, but technology is also affecting the subject matter itself. In the US, the mathematics curriculum is being revised in some states so that pupils are not anymore taught the standard multiplication and division algorithms. Such impacts of technology in the teaching of mathematics are profound, and, if not applied wisely, may lead to undesired consequences. During 2008-2009 the JEM Network will organize events offering a venue to debate such matters also. This is to prepare for the final JEM event, a virtual training camp for mathematics teachers in Europe.

IMPACT & SUSTAINABILITY

Joining Educational Mathematics is a thematic network that attempts to strengthen the connections and collaboration of those working to advance to use of technology in mathematics teaching and learning. In this respect, the European dimension of the network is vital to the creation of new research activities and new consortia pursuing common interests. Partners of JEM have been exposed to a varied combination of expertise within the network and have been able to profit from these by becoming involved in proposals both at national and international level. Examples of this impact are clear, for instance, from the recent developments in UOC, and in TU/e and UvA.

The main vehicle for the JEM community to fuel cooperation and communication is the web portal. Each partner has full control on the items published on the website and distributed to the subscribers. Contributions are welcome from all registered members on topics and activities of interest to JEM. The section of the portal on "News Headlines" is aggregating content from partner sites running RSS feeds. These are specifically encouraged since they allow members to only submit news and updates on their websites and distribute them automatically, likewise for blogs, which are now available under "Planet JEM".

FURTHER INFORMATION

To obtain up-to-date information on the ongoing activities organized by JEM, consult the web pages at <http://www.jem-thematic.net> or subscribe to the JEM newsfeed for the specific area of your interest.

The list of meetings is online at <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/about/meetings>, while all the network publications, including this report and other deliverables, are archived at <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/publications>.

For contacting the network's coordinator directly use the contact form at <http://www.jem-thematic.net/en/contact>.

